

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE MANAGEMENT OF THE PENITENTIARY SYSTEM IN ROMANIA AS A RESULT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Purpose – *The main objective of this paper is to assess the progress made within a state institution in the field of national defence and security in Romania in a crisis situation, such as the COVID-19 pandemic.*

Methodology/approach - *We have used a secondary analysis as the main research method to obtain the essential information about the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the institution, collecting both quantitative and qualitative data. Additionally, participatory observation helped us extract the most relevant elements from the pandemic period, based on which we have conducted a series of analyses.*

Findings – *The results obtained highlight the causal relationship between the efficiency of the managerial system of the prison system in Romania and the digitization of the institution, as a response to the crisis situation generated by the COVID-19 pandemic.*

Research limitations/implications – *The main limitations are related to the method of data collection, the information obtained from document analysis, most of which are public documents, which may be scarce or may be presented in a favourable light for the institution.*

Originality/value - *The originality of the work is outlined in researching the managerial mechanisms applied in Romanian prisons during the pandemic period and how these have been sustained over time.*

Practical implications – *The implications consist in conducting a comparative analysis of managerial practices, before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.*

Key words: *management, penitentiary system, pandemic*

Introduction

This paper explores the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the evolution of the prison system in Romania. To obtain conclusive results, the study considered the period from 2019 to 2023, mainly analysing the annual reports of the National Administration of Penitentiaries. The COVID-19 pandemic period brought a series of challenges for organizations globally. Thus, organizations everywhere have had to rethink their management strategies and adapt to the crisis situation that had emerged (Marcelo F. Aebi and Mélanie M. Tiago, 2020).

If we talk about management practiced in public institutions in Romania, we can also discuss its rigidity, generated by the applicable legislative norms, especially since the institution in

question manages a sensitive segment of the population (Alina-Elena Ionaşcu (Huluba), 2021). As a result, the pandemic period was difficult to control in the prison administration system, a closed, overcrowded system where social distancing can rarely be maintained, with an increased risk of airborne transmission of the virus. Consequently, legislative interventions were needed to facilitate the implementation of prevention and control measures against SARS-CoV-2 infection, adapted to the specific nature of the prison system in Romania and the existing situations in detention facilities (Ştefan and Grecu, 2020).

The pandemic has highlighted the existing weaknesses in the Romanian prison system and emphasised the need for reforms to improve conditions in prisons, access to medical care, and reintegration programs, by developing a prison system that ensures respect for the fundamental rights of incarcerated individuals and facilitates their reintegration into society after release. Among the vulnerabilities that have emerged during the reference period, the most important ones have been related to overcrowding in detention facilities (Ştefan and Grecu, 2020) and the poor digitization of procedures, which are further addressed.

Prison overcrowding

Prison overcrowding played a crucial role in the rapid spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, laying the groundwork for an environment conducive to the amplification of infectious diseases. Being a relatively closed-circuit structure, the COVID-19 pandemic was treated as a major challenge by the managerial system from the onset of the first cases in Europe, when only a few prison administrations were not affected by COVID-19 infections: 15 institutions reported infections among both staff and inmates, while 14 reported infections only among staff (Marcelo F. Aebi and Mélanie M. Tiago, 2020). Thus, the existing risk factors that can amplify and spread infectious diseases in the carceral environment are outlined, such as: penitentiary mobility, pre-existing conditions among incarcerated individuals, and complex security procedures.

Figure 1 presents the evolution of prison population in Romania within the interval 2019-2023 (pre Covid-19 and post-Covid 19), which shows a gradual increase from 20 578 to 23 360 persons, recording a total increase of 13.5%.

Fig.1 The evolution of the prison population in Romania
Source: (ANP, 2020), (ANP, 2021), (ANP, 2022).

To prevent detention spaces from becoming infection hotspots, a series of prevention and emergency intervention measures were taken to delay the entry of the coronavirus into the carceral environment as much as possible. Thus, the first confirmed case of coronavirus among incarcerated individuals appeared on September 24, 2020, approximately 7 months after the confirmation of the first case in Romania, on February 26, 2020, and approximately 5 months after the first cases appeared among employees (Adrian Streinu-Cercel et al, 2020).

Taking into account that investments in infrastructure are costly and long-term, it was necessary to identify quick solutions. The health security measures aimed to:

- establishing quarantine sections in the six healthcare units of the penitentiary administration;
- efficiently managing the held spaces to control inmates with a high degree of vulnerability;
- conducting epidemiological screening;
- establishing a technical-medical support group to monitor the implementation of the action plan;
- increasing the budget for the purchase of necessary equipment for prevention and infection control;
- legislative adaptation regarding the increase in staff (without competition, for a specified period) in crisis situations;
- digitization of procedures (Ștefan and Grecu, 2020).

From our point of view, the most sensitive areas, in terms of the necessity of interpersonal relationships, affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, were represented by the Social Reintegration Department and the Human Resources Management Department, both having a major impact on the optimal conduct of activities.

The existing epidemiological context at the international level posed a particular challenge in terms of the need to implement alternative communication methods both within the system, referring here to communication between units and communication with the management team at the central headquarters, and between incarcerated individuals and their families. The solution identified to reduce the risks caused by social interactions comes from the digital sphere and is represented by moving physical interactions into the digital sphere through specialized applications such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Cisco Webex Meetings, Skype. (ANP, 2020).

On the human resources management front, to supplement staff for efficient crisis management, a total of 115 positions were filled without competition for a duration of six months in key sectors: medical and operational, across 33 units. The process resulted in the filling of 67 positions out of a total of 976 candidates, including 48 in the medical sector and 19 in the operational sector. Also, aiming to intensify efforts to ensure the necessary personnel, at the end of 2020, 1413 vacant positions were opened for competition from external sources, along with 185 from internal sources. This culminated in 1925 recruitments in 2021 (considering the positions opened for competition in 2021). Among all these newly recruited prison officers from external sources, numerous were rookies, and in 2022, for the first time, initiation courses or training courses were organized for 1086 prison officers, online or in a hybrid system (ANP, 2020), (ANP, 2021), (ANP, 2022).

It is important to mention that the trends have persisted, and although the number of annual recruitments is decreasing, courses have continued in an online/hybrid format, given their effectiveness. Practice has shown that conducting initiation courses online/hybrid facilitates the integration of prison officers into their work and team, creates an emergency lever for interventions in case of force majeure, and even though courses are no longer held in person, much more emphasis is placed on the practical aspects of the activities.

From the perspective of the social reintegration sector, technology comes precisely to support the main goal of the National Administration of Penitentiaries, which is to involve incarcerated individuals in activities in the field of psychosocial assistance, education, training, and employment to spend as little time as possible in detention rooms, given European recommendations, which foresee a number of 8 hours per day for reintegration activities (ANP, 2021). Ultimately, the aim is to reduce the rate of recidivism.

According to Article 41 of the Penal Code, there is recidivism when, after the finality of a conviction decision to a prison sentence exceeding one year or life imprisonment until rehabilitation or the expiration of the rehabilitation term, the convicted person commits another intentional or exceeded intention offense, for which the law provides a prison sentence of one year or more or life imprisonment (Ministry of Justice apud Penal Code, 2023).

Although integrating technology into social reintegration activities has been quite challenging, we can observe a downward trend in the recidivism rate in recent years, from t0 (the pandemic year, 2020) to the present (see figure 2). This indicates how, out of the necessity to adapt to crisis situations, the management system has contributed to reducing the recidivism rate through the digitization of this atypical environment.

Fig.2 Recidivism rate in Romania
 Source: (ANP, 2020), (ANP, 2021), (ANP, 2022).

To compensate for the limitation of activities of the Social Reintegration Directorate during the state of emergency, socio-educational activities for incarcerated individuals involved the creation and broadcast, using the radio-TV studios within the penitentiary units, of their own programs. These programs served an educational, informative, and moral-religious role, replacing the classic occupations from which the inmates were deprived. They contributed to maintaining the reintegration programs for the prison population in Romania and implementing the strategic objectives outlined in the National Strategy for the Social Reintegration of Persons Deprived of Liberty, approved by Government Decision no. 430/2020 (ANP, 2020).

The technologization of interactions within prisons

During the state of emergency, due to the suspension of visitations, maintaining the connection of inmates with family members, relatives, or other persons was ensured through phone calls and online communications. In this regard, the duration and number of phone calls were increased, and the number of online communications allowed for inmates was supplemented, regardless of disciplinary status and frequency of family contact, corresponding to the number of visits they were entitled to, depending on the execution regime or category they belonged to. Through appropriate institutional measures, a reduction in the rates for phone calls made by inmates was achieved, but only during the state of emergency (ANP reports, 2020).

Video conferences for inmates have become an important means of communication during the pandemic, when personal visits were restricted or suspended in many prisons around the world. In Romania, as well as in other countries, these video conferences were used to allow inmates to maintain contact with their families and to communicate with lawyers or other relevant individuals (Marcelo F. Aebi and Mélanie M. Tiago, 2020). They have become a valuable resource in prisons to facilitate communication and access to essential services during the pandemic. However, it is important to find a balance between the use of technology and ensuring a humane and fair approach to the treatment of inmates.

Given the increase in the number of hearings via video conference due to requests from the courts, the 47 terminals dedicated to video conferencing for the hearing of inmates became insufficient. As a solution, an additional 86 access accounts for the video conferencing system belonging to the Special Telecommunications Service were provided, using the "Polycom RealPresence Desktop" application, which allows the enrollment of computers as video conferencing terminals for inmate hearings. Figure 3 shows a significant increase in 2020 compared to 2019, when only 1,484 hearings were conducted via video conference with the courts (ANP reports, 2020).

The causal relationship between the changes made during the pandemic period and the reduction in the recidivism rate is direct, from our point of view, and highlights the increased efficiency of penitentiary system procedures.

Fig.3 The evolution of the video conferences in Romania

Source: (ANP, 2020), (ANP, 2021), (ANP, 2022).

Conclusions

The paper aimed to highlight the progress made within the penitentiary system, driven by the pandemic situation. Thus, the paper contributes to identifying the approaches and management methods that can ensure institutional evolution at the level of the National Administration of Penitentiaries. Additionally, the study can facilitate the improvement of the legislative system in Romania.

By engaging in this endeavour, we have observed the leap made by the penitentiary system in a short period of time from a conservative management style to an innovative type of management, given the measures taken and especially the technologization of procedures.

The limitations considered at the beginning of the research did not represent an impediment, given that the data taken from the activity reports were only statistical data. The analysis was conducted objectively and impartially, following the steps of a scientific research.

A new direction that can be explored in detail, building on this research, is the realization of a study at the European level, focusing on the comparative analysis of the practices of European Union member states and Romania, with the aim of identifying best practices that can be adopted within the Romanian penitentiary system.

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